

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS, AND INFORMATICS

MULTI-SPEAKER SPEECH SYNTHESIS SYSTEMS: A SURVEY

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Abstract

The earliest invention that is a predecessor to modern speech synthesis was created over 200 years ago. Nowadays with the improvement of technology, it is a thriving field with many directions for improvement and research. In this paper, we describe a number of multi-speaker speech synthesis systems, while investigating the field's past and various modern methods of synthesis.

Keywords: survey, multi-speaker, speech synthesis, text-to-speech.

Introduction

The modern area of speech synthesis, also known as text-to-speech (TTS), has significantly advanced. In the past, people tried to synthesize human speech using various inventions like windpipes, tried imitating vocal organs and concatenating pre-recorded speech. Earliest attempts to synthesize human speech were recorded in the 1700s and used organ-like instruments that could pronounce vowels, interrupting and compressing air flow to imitate human sounds [29]. First fully-electric synthesis system was created in 1922 [30], and the first speech synthesizer was created 15 years later [29, 30].

Later, in the field of speech synthesis has advanced, with the introduction of such synthesis methods like articulatory synthesis, formant synthesis and the invention of the first text-to-speech device [30] - and with the discovery of statistical parametric speech synthesis (SPSS), and later, along with the advancements of technology, neural TTS, the discoveries in the field have improved significantly in terms of quality, quantity and availability [32].

Traditionally, neural speech synthesis models follow the framework from SPSS and consist of three parts: a text analyzer, that takes text as input and outputs linguistic features; an acoustic model, that turns the linguistic features into acoustic features; and a vocoder that outputs sound from acoustic features [1]. Many of the modern models, neural models in particular, implement an "end-to-end" approach: they output acoustic features, directly from text. There are also models that synthesize voice directly from text - systems like that are called "fully end-to-end" [11].

Due to massive recent advancements in the field, there are many synthesis models that are focused on certain aspects of speech synthesis. Some of the modern synthesis models can produce speech of quality indistinguishable from human speech [31]. Other models are focused on transferring styles and emotions [5]. Some papers describe models that are able to perform code-switch, switching languages mid-sentence [4]. There are also models that are capable of producing high-quality speech from a low amount of data [7]. This

way, more and more of the recent systems are able to combine such aspects of speech synthesis, being able to create multi-speaker models capable of producing high-quality output with low amounts of data, while also implementing code-switch [8].

The focus of this paper is on multi-speaker speech synthesis models. These models are capable of outputting speech with different voices, extracting timbre from sound along with other vocal features, like pause, style, etc. and outputting speech with extracted features. We have picked 10 papers published within the last 6 years, observing which could help us get a clear picture of the current state of this field, discover the areas that could be improved upon, and find areas for more research.

Analysis of Multi-Speaker Synthesis Systems

In [1], Authors state that generative adversarial networks (GAN) showed powerful performance in several image domains, and that it was adopted successfully in speech domain. They have proposed a high-fidelity multi-speaker TTS model that adopts the adversarial training method to non-autoregressive multi-speaker TTS models - FastSpeech [12] and FastSpeech2 [13], in addition to automatic scaling methods for feature matching loss used in adversarial training. Joint conditional and unconditional (JCU) discriminator [14] with speaker embedding as a condition was used as the model's discriminator to learn the general characteristic of mel spectrogram along with speaker specific characteristics.

GANSpeech was trained on a studio-quality internal corpus and used VocGAN [15] as its vocoder. The model had significantly outperformed the baseline multi-speaker models, and showed a better MOS score than the speaker-specific fine-tuned FastSpeech2 [13] in the subjective listening tests. The model was found to be able to synthesize high-fidelity speech of multiple speakers as a single model without an additional module for enhancing TTS model or any speaker-specific fine-tuning.

The authors of [2] describe TDASS, Target Domain Adaptation Speech Synthesis Framework that is

based on Tacotron2 [17]. They are improving upon SPSS methods and models like FastSpeech [12] and Tacotron [16] that require large corpora with high-quality utterances to produce speech that would be as natural as human speech. The model also includes a special gradient reversal layer that reverses the gradient for non-target speakers. This way, the authors have addressed the issues of voice similarity and optimization for low-resource situations.

The model was compared to its baseline version, Tacotron2 [17], and the experiment results on a Chinese speech corpus show the proposed method outperforms the baseline methods, with higher VSS scores in general, and better MOS and MCD scores under low-resource conditions.

The authors of [3] extend the functionality of ClariNet [18] by turning it into a multi-speaker model. This is done by adding speaker embeddings as a bias to each part of ClariNet's [18] network. Evaluated by MOS, the model outperforms state-of-the-art models like DeepVoice2 [19] and DeepVoice3 [20] despite using fewer convolution layers. The authors have also managed to produce a high-quality synthesized voice and retain speaker identities.

Shared speaker embeddings of the model can learn discriminative features of the speakers, since they serve as a bias to each component of the model. The output was further tested using well-trained speaker classification and evaluation models, resulting in equal error rates similar to those of the ground truth. In conclusion, the authors have also noted that the model is also capable of voice cloning.

The aim of [4] is to achieve cross-lingual multi-speaker TTS in English and Mandarin while using limited bilingual data. Since collecting huge data for multi-speaker cross-lingual synthesis is costly, it is essential to address the cross-lingual synthesis under low-resource data scenarios. The authors of this paper propose two training scenarios: cross-lingual synthesis with sufficient data and cross-lingual synthesis with limited data per speaker. The model designed for sufficient-data cases has a Tacotron-based structure that uses shared phonemic representations associated with numeric language ID codes, and the limited data model has a non-autoregressive many-to-many voice conversion module to address multi-speaker synthesis for data-insufficient cases.

TTS regarding multiple languages is more complicated due to different grapheme representations across languages, and as a result of evaluating multiple input representation methods, using phoneme units had been decided as the best method for these scenarios.

The models' performance results for Chinese, English and code-switching sentences are evaluated by multiple criteria using MOS: naturalness, intelligibility and similarity.

In the data-sufficient scenario, quality of speech reaches around 4 points when synthesizing audio samples in the target speaker's native language, while the performance degrades when generating cross-lingual speech for monolingual speakers. Most speaker similarity MOS are around 4, while scores lower than 4 can be observed in cross-lingual cases.

The authors have noticed that the synthesized speech sounds exactly like a foreign speaker would, speaking another language with an accent from their native language. The result indicates that using a bilingual dataset with their proposed model can significantly improve cross-lingual speech synthesis for monolingual speakers.

In the data-insufficient scenario, the lack of data is compensated by using multiple feature extractors in order to preserve speech quality: the bottleneck extractor and the speaker embedding extractor.

As a result, the model has demonstrated outstanding results in terms of intelligibility performance of the voice conversion system. All synthesis scenarios of this system, including cross-lingual and code-switching synthesis, have achieved a MOS above 4. Also, the voice conversion module has been found to maintain the voice characteristics well in data-limited cases.

In [5], the authors create a model that learns emotion classes from just two speakers then generalizes these classes to other speakers from whom no emotional data was seen. The core of the problem is that obtaining emotional speech on a similar scale can be challenging and expensive in comparison to non-emotional speech. The (internal) corpus contains the voices of two emotional speakers, and 8 neutral speakers in mandarin with four emotion classes defined: angry, happy, sad and neutral.

The authors have found out that the system had learned to associate emotions mostly with emotional speakers, making the authors look for a way to represent emotion that is detached from speaker identity, discovering that an information bottleneck encourages learning acoustically important features not already present among the conditioning inputs, therefore detaching the latent code from speaker identity.

The model based on FastSpeech is evaluated with MOS in terms of naturalness, speaker similarity and the clarity of emotional expressiveness and compared to baseline models. In terms of naturalness and speaker similarity, little difference among systems for emotional speakers and significant improvements for neutral speakers were observed. As for emotional expressiveness, the authors observed significant improvement in emotional expressiveness over the baselines.

Similar to [5], [6] proposes a style transfer model. The model is able to transfer the style of one speaker to the timbre of another and increase the diversity of synthetic speech by providing the ability to adjust the value of prosody features like pitch, duration and energy. It is a typical attention-based seq2seq framework, in which the backbone of the encoder-decoder structure is based on a modified Tacotron2 [17]. WaveRNN [22] is adopted to reconstruct waveforms from predicted spectrograms.

The authors use data from an internal Mandarin multi-speaker corpus, in which each speaker has a unique speaking style. The model is evaluated using MOS and is compared to two similar state-of-the-art style transfer methods, achieving generally higher scores than its counterparts. The authors have also conducted an ablation study, in which dropping of the duration brings the biggest drop in the evaluation.

Msdtron, a high-capability speech synthesis system is a model that is proposed by the authors in [7] to solve the issue of the costly, time-consuming process of collecting professional high-quality and high-consistency voice data. The model uses a representation of the harmonic structure of speech designed to directly guide the learning of harmonics in mel-spectrogram, and a modification of long-short term memory (LSTM) [23] called “conditional gated LSTM” (CGLSTM) that is also proposed in the paper, controls the flow of text content information through the network. The model’s text encoder is an augmented Tacotron2 [17] encoder.

To train the model, the authors use AISHELL-3 [24], a public multi-speaker mandarin corpus. MOS test was carried out to evaluate its performance in voice quality of speech and speaker similarity. As a result, the proposed excitation spectrogram was found to be much more effective than the simple use of pitch and energy, and the system outperformed the baseline largely both on the voice quality and the speaker similarity.

The authors of [8] propose a lightweight multi-speaker multilingual speech synthesis system (LightTTS) that can quickly synthesize the Chinese, English or code-switch speech of multiple speakers in a non-autoregressive generation manner. It combines the advantages of lightweight convolutional neural networks and self-attention layers to reduce the number of parameters and the computational complexity. It is able to achieve good performance with fewer parameters through the lightweight neural network architecture and sequence-level knowledge distillation technology.

Using x-vectors, language ID, and language embeddings, the model can quickly synthesize the speech of multiple speakers in multiple languages. It inherits all the advantages of FastSpeech [12], including fast speech synthesis speed, controllability of the generated speech, and few words skipping problems.

Trained using LibriTTS, THCH S30 and Aidatang 200zh datasets for english, chinese and code-switch datasets, LightTTS is then compared to Tacotron2 [17], Transformer TTS [28] and FastSpeech [12], and has demonstrated close performance during MOS evaluation. The model has also achieved performance close to FastSpeech [12] in the code-switch case.

The goal of [9] is to create a model able to transfer the style and emotion from reference speech recorded by other speakers. The authors address this problem with a two-stage framework composed of a text-to-style-and-emotion (Text2SE) module and a style- and emotion-to-wave (SE2Wave) module. They also introduce a semi-supervised training strategy to leverage data from multiple speakers.

The task has three challenges: style and emotion patterns are both reflected in speech prosody and thus highly entangled; difficulty of obtaining expressive data labeled with both emotion and speaking styles; novel text content during inference is different from the reference signal selected in the training data.

The authors solve these issues by: adopting the multi-label binary vector and mutual information (MI) minimization to decouple the style, emotion, and

speaker factors; introducing a semi-supervised training strategy to leverage expressive data from multiple speakers, including emotion-labeled, style-labeled, and unlabeled data; propose an attention-based reference selection approach, which avoids the difficulty of manual reference selection.

The model is trained on the internal corpora with emotion-labeled, style-labeled, and unlabeled data and is evaluated in comparison to MR-Tacotron [26] and Referee [27], demonstrating better naturalness, emotion similarity, speaker similarity and style similarity. The models are also compared using CER (character error rate) and Cosine Similarity objective evaluation methods, where the proposed method also displays good results.

The aim of the authors of [10] is to improve the disentanglement effectiveness of timbres and styles, and to remove the reliance on single-speaker multi-style corpus. To achieve this, a simple but effective timbre and style disentanglement method is proposed.

The FastSpeech2 [13] network is employed as the backbone network, with explicit duration, pitch, and energy trajectory to represent the style. MelGAN [28] is used as the neural vocoder to convert acoustic features to speech. Each speaker’s data is considered as a separate and isolated style, then a speaker embedding and a style embedding are added to the FastSpeech2 [13] network to learn disentangled representations.

The authors note that it is important to prevent style embedding from leaking into the backbone network, meaning that style embeddings should only be used for style feature prediction and never be exposed to the backbone network. Also, instead of speaker level normalization, utterance level pitch and energy normalization are used to remove speaker identity from the style features for better timbre and style disentanglement.

The MOS evaluation of the model was focused on speaker and style similarity; and conducted with a model trained on three open-sourced and three internal corpora, the latter having different styles: news-broadcasting, children story, and story-telling. As a result, speaker similarity of generated speeches in different styles were found to be very high and consistent. Also, an ablation study comparing generated speech with speaker level normalization and utterance level pitch and energy normalization has revealed strong preference of the latter by the listeners, which was reflected on the speaker similarity score.

Discussion

The papers describe various established synthesis models like Tacotron and FastSpeech, discovering various methods and areas for improvement. Using available data we have found that the majority of the papers are focused on adapting for scenarios with low-quality or limited data, with others focusing on expressiveness, multilingualism and building a lightweight model. It should also be noted that most of the models use corpora on languages with abundant resources, like Chinese and English. The comparison of the architectures is displayed in [Table 1].

Table 1

The Comparison of Architectures in Analyzed Researches

#	Name	Architecture	Corpus	Language	Metrics
1	GANSpeech: Adversarial Training for High-Fidelity Multi-Speaker Speech Synthesis [1]	GAN	Internal	Korean	PESQ, F0 RMSE, MCD
2	TDASS: Target Domain Adaptation Speech Synthesis Framework for Multi-speaker Low-Resource TTS [2]	modified Tacotron2	Internal	Chinese	MOS, MCD
3	Multi-Speaker End-to-End Speech Synthesis [3]	modified ClariNet	VCTK	English	MOS
4	Cross-lingual multi-speaker speech synthesis with limited bilingual training data [4]	Tacotron, FastSpeech	LJSpeech, DB1	English, Chinese	MOS, EER
5	Multi-Speaker Emotional Speech Synthesis with Fine-Grained Prosody Modeling [5]	modified FastSpeech	Internal	Chinese	MOS
6	Multi-speaker multi-style text-to-speech synthesis with single-speaker single-style training data scenarios [6]	modified Tacotron2	Internal	Chinese	MOS
7	Msdtron: a high-capability multi-speaker speech synthesis system for diverse data using characteristic information [7]	modified Tacotron2	AISHHELL-3	Chinese	MOS
8	Light-TTS: Lightweight Multi-Speaker Multi-Lingual Text-to-Speech [8]	own	LibriTTS, THCHS30, Aidatatang_200zh	English, Chinese, Code-switch	MOS, MCD
9	Multi-Speaker Expressive Speech Synthesis via Multiple Factors Decoupling [9]	own, Text2SE & SE2Wave	M30S3, M3E6, M30U	Chinese	MOS, CER, cosine similarity
10	Multi-Speaker Multi-Style Speech Synthesis with Timbre and Style Disentanglement [10]	modified FastSpeech2, MelGAN - vocoder	CSMSC, MFA- Originbeat	Chinese	MOS

Conclusion

We have conducted a survey of the speech synthesis field and analyzed a number of papers describing various multi-speaker models focused on improving different aspects of the field, along with its history and different methods.

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